

Effective Implementation of Heads of Schools Recognition Leadership Strategy on Improving Teachers' Level of Commitment in Community Based Secondary Schools in Kilimanjaro Region - Tanzania

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Abstract:- This study examined the effective implementation of Heads of Schools (HoS) Recognition Leadership Strategy on improving teachers' level of commitment in community-based secondary schools (CBSS) in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania. Instructional leadership theory guided the study. Qualitative research approach was employed by using a correlational cross-sectional survey design. The study employed teachers and student' questionnaires for data collection from a target population of 225 community-based secondary schools in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania. Respondents were 360, of whom 115 were teachers out of 120 who were selected and 240 were students from three district councils selected by simple random sampling technique in the region. The questionnaires for data collection were validated before data collection by using experts in the research field at Mwenge Catholic University (MWECAU) and others in the field of education administration. Questionnaires' reliability was ensured by using Cronbach's alpha technique at 0.974 and 0.906 for the teachers and students respectively after pilot testing study. Data were analysed using frequency, percentage, and the mean score presented in tables. The findings indicated that at a mean of 4.1 (82%), teachers agreed that the HoS recognition strategy enabled them to work hard, and as a result, the students' academic performance was raised from time to time. This implied that the greater majority (82%) of HoS in CBSS in Kilimanjaro Region know the implications of recognising teachers in their schools, and they use this strategy. The Chi Square technique used to test hypothesis of p-value of 0.019 at 0.05 consequently null hypothesis was rejected hence, there was a significant relationship between HoS recognition leadership strategy and teachers' levels of commitment. The study concluded that there was a significant relationship between HoS recognition leadership strategy and teachers' level of commitment in community-based secondary schools in the Kilimanjaro region of Tanzania. The study recommended that Hos should employ a recognition leadership strategy in order to improve teachers' levels of commitment. Furthermore, teachers should spend more of their time assisting students' learning.

Keywords:- Head of School (HoS) Recognition Leadership Strategy, teachers' level of commitment, Quality Education and Effective Implementation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Kilimanjaro Region, like any other region in Tanzania, has a major role in providing quality education for sustainable development of her community and entire country. More efforts have been made to ensure good investment in teaching and learning activities. As a result, 225 (out of 3,683 nationwide, which is 5.8%) secondary schools are now found in the region (BEST 2020). In the region, each ward has one community-based secondary school (CBSS), which enables a large number of students completing standard seven with a pass mark (Grade C in the National Examination Results) to be enrolled in these schools. With this investment, teachers are still considered an influential factor in quality education that enhances students' best learning processes, regardless of other factors and challenges present (Akbari & Malagi, 2017).

Teachers' commitment to providing a high-quality education is reflected in their effort and involvement (Mpaata & Mpaata, 2019). Teachers who are committed demonstrate various organizational and personal outcomes, such as turnover, performance, and their intention to stay or leave (Victor, 2017). In CBSS, a committed teacher was regarded as a great asset. Towards this end, different scholars, such as Ayandoja, Aina, and Idowu (2017), observed that a committed teacher was hardworking and less inclined to leave the workplace.

Moreover, teachers' commitment can be measured by how involved they are and how much they support the decision. Commitment is a crucial aspect to be enhanced and nurtured among school teachers. At the school level, teachers' commitment is seen as having an impact on the success of education and schooling in the future as well as school effectiveness, teacher satisfaction, and teacher retention, as well as job performance, absenteeism, and staff turnover (Mpaata & Mpaata, 2018). At the student level, it is discovered that teachers' commitment levels have an effect on

students' academic performance and school-related attitudes. (Mahzan & Nordin, 2021).

According to Mpaata & Mpaata (2018), the level of a teacher's commitment is determined by how much time and effort they devote to assisting students in learning regardless of their academic challenges or social backgrounds and encourage their social integration in the classroom (Lai & Han, 2020). They make a connection between their scholars' academic success and the symbolic incentives they get from other people, including other students, parents, the administrator, and district authorities. As a result, teachers' commitment can be described as their sense of devotion to the school as a workplace through upholding its ideals and objectives.

Additionally, several stakeholders reported teachers' levels of dedication to the teaching and learning process at various times and on various occasions, which eventually

hampered the desired educational outcomes. Example: Twaweza (2016) reported a high rate of teachers' absenteeism in school and class that ranged between 11% and 30% in Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda, while in Tanzania in particular the rate of teachers' absenteeism was high at 25%. Bestowing to the Teachers Service Department's (TSD) 2017 report, teacher misconduct was one of the major impediments to teachers' dedication and subpar instruction.

Additionally, other education stakeholders, such as the Northern-Eastern Education Quality Assurance Department (EQAD), Kilimanjaro Regional Education Officer (REO), and Moshi Municipal Secondary Education Officer (MSEO), claimed in their 2018–2020 school visit reports and assessments that teachers were lacking commitment to their job. This was reported by Kilimanjaro REO during the HoS Region Meeting on March 16, 2020, as found in Table 1.

Table 1: Indicators of lack of Teachers' Commitment

Year	Teachers'					
	Absenteeism (%)	Unprepared Lessons (%)	Assistance to students (%)	Quarrels with HoS (%)	Disciplinary cases (%)	Family excuses (%)
2018	21	32	78	13	8	36
2019	18	28	82	11	3	38
2020	20	24	84	7	5	27
Average	19.7	28.0	81.3	10.3	5.3	33.7

Source: Kilimanjaro school follow-up visit report 2020 by REO

Table 1 shows a great fall in teachers' commitment to their work. For three years, school follow-up leaders reports revealed 19.7% of teachers' absenteeism, 28.0% were not preparing their academic teaching documents regularly, 18.7% did not dedicate their time to assist students' academic and life challenges, 10.3% had quarrels with their HoS, about 5.3% had an indiscipline case attended by the Teachers' Service Commission (TSC), and 33.7% had some excuses at their workstation due to family issues.

The observed teachers' absenteeism tendency, teaching without proper lesson preparation, lack of time to assist students having learning challenges, and others with indiscipline cases pertaining to their core education function in school, indicates a low level of commitment to work. This requires HoS to employ an effective leadership strategy to alleviate the situation. If the situation remains unchanged with time, it will lower students' academic achievement in their final examinations, and the whole goal of them being in school for four years will end up in vain. The government budget invested in education and the education goal will never be attained, and the future and dreams of students will never be reached.

The primary responsibility of the HoS at the school is to use a variety of tactics when supervising teachers to ensure that the teaching and learning process is effective and that they are dedicated to their positions. With effective HoS leadership strategies in place, it is expected that teachers will be committed to their job by maximizing their time to assist students with learning difficulties (Mahzan & Nordin, 2021).

Due to this, the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology (MoEST) made the decision to launch the Secondary School Management Toolkit (SSMT) as a practical manual designed to give HoS various managerial skills that they can use in their daily supervision to increase teachers' commitment. (URT, 2015).

One of the HoS leadership strategies proposed by SSMT is the recognition strategy. The strategy by itself requires HoS to have different ways of recognizing and appreciating teachers' performance. Official rewards can also be given to teachers during special school events like graduation day or Parents' Day after having a clear and open system for how the best performers can be identified. Other recognitions can be in the form of oral words or a letter of appreciation. This study evaluated the leadership approach of HoS recognition's effectiveness in raising teachers' levels of commitment in community-based secondary schools in Tanzania's Kilimanjaro area.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The lack of clearly visible intended outcomes from the teaching and learning process has raised questions about the level of dedication among teachers in Tanzania's secondary community-based schools. For instance, Twaweza (2016) found that teacher absenteeism is a problem, with rates ranging from 11% to 30% in Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda, with Tanzania's rates being higher than those of all three nations with 25% low attendance. Additionally, according to the Kilimanjaro Regional Education Officer (REO) school

visit report for the years 2018 to 2020, which was presented to the HoS meeting on March 16, 2020, teachers were absent from the classroom 19.7% of the time on average, 28% did not prepare lesson plans, and 18.7% did not devote enough time to helping students who were having trouble learning. Furthermore, 10.3% had quarrels with HoS, 5.3% had disciplinary cases, and 33.7% had family excuses that hindered their commitment to work.

This fact led to a number of inquiries on the commitment of teachers to equipping themselves with all relevant paperwork and the students' course materials before class. Do HoS supervisors monitor instructors' adherence to their profession's performance standards? Do teachers receive praise and rewards for their effective instruction? Despite all of these investigations, there was still a lack of apparent tenacity in tackling the problems, and insufficient research had been done in the Kilimanjaro region to deal with this issue. The extent to which teachers execute their professional teaching responsibilities indicates their level of commitment. In order to fill this gap, the current study examined how effective HoS leadership strategies were implemented to improve teachers' levels of commitment in CBSS in the Kilimanjaro region of Tanzania.

A. Research Question

One research question (RQ) that was used to lead this study was as follows::

RQ₁: How does the HoS recognition leadership strategy improve teachers' levels of commitment in community-based secondary schools in the Kilimanjaro Region?

B. Research Hypothesis

This study was guided by one research hypothesis (H1), as follows: -

H₁: There is a significant relationship between HoS recognition leadership strategy and teachers' levels of commitment.

III. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study was intended to give the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology relevant information about the effectiveness of the HoS Recognition Leadership Strategy in raising teachers' levels of commitment in Tanzania's community-based secondary schools. This feedback would be used to revise the Secondary School Management Tool Kit (SSMT) about the applicability of the strategy towards its expected outcomes. Some adjustments found in this study would be incorporated into the toolkit in order to get another edition. The revised edition would be more practical as a guideline for HoSs of community-based secondary schools in Tanzania for better supervision of the provision of quality education.

The study was also significant for educational stakeholders like HoS, teachers, and students. HoS, as the key education supervisors at school level, would be enriched by the findings of the study. The findings suggested important techniques or aspects under the recognition HoS leadership strategy that, when taken care of, would increase teachers'

level of commitment. On the teachers' side, they also benefited from students' feedback on areas where they felt assisted by teachers and found their learning smooth and more effective. Also, the study highlighted areas where students were not well assisted by their teachers while they were in need of a better learning process. On the students' side, they benefited from this study as it was expected that the outcome of the supervision of the provision of quality education would be the better academic performance of students, which would give them a chance to join higher levels of learning and bring a better return on their educational investment.

The results of this study were also anticipated to contribute to the body of knowledge and comprehension of the HoS leadership theories and tactics that were examined and criticized. The fundamental goal of establishing community-based secondary schools in Tanzania was to provide high-quality instruction, so when these findings are put into practice, greater outcomes are anticipated in these areas. This study also provided evidence for the instructional leadership hypothesis, which supports the idea that educational leaders should play a role in enhancing the teaching and learning process, in this case through praising instructors' accomplishments. This increases their dedication to their work.

IV. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is based on the instructional leadership theory, which emphasizes the importance of an educational leader in strengthening teachers' commitment to improve the teaching and learning process. Having an improved teaching and learning process as a result of effective HoS leadership supervision can lead to high academic achievement in students' examinations. Thomas Sergiovanni, a pioneer who created the instructional leadership theory, classified the power of leadership into five areas in the early 1980s: technical, human, educational, symbolic, and cultural. (Sarkaya & Erdoan, 2016). The technical dimension includes leadership functions such as organisational development activities, time management, and planning.

On the other hand, the human component deals with interpersonal interactions, including the principal's ability to motivate others and his or her communication skills (Mukhtar & Fook, 2020). The principal's instructional role in directing the teaching and learning process falls under the category of instructional power. The ability of the instructional leader to act as a role model for what is vital for the school and what fulfills the school's aims as well as to integrate with the organization's ideas and values is highlighted by symbolic and cultural powers. (Wasserman & Yehoshua, 2016). Because of these requirements, a HoS must effectively serve as an example of how the organizational vision and goals of the school should be achieved. Therefore, it is important to have a specific strategy towards each end (i.e., teachers' commitment) and a thorough assessment of how far they are effective.

This theory observed at how an instructional leader prioritizes instruction and learning, creates and communicates school goals, plans and oversees the implementation of the curriculum, keeps a close eye on students' progress, maintains high visibility and a hands-on approach, and gives teachers and students incentives (Mgonja, 2017; Choi & Gil, 2017). This study found that in community-based secondary schools in Kilimanjaro, Tanzania, the HoS leadership recognition strategy as proposed by SSMT gives HoS a room to spare time for sharing with a specific teacher to find out strengths and challenges that affect the teacher's performance and find together a better way forward that increases teachers' level of commitment..

The instructional leadership theory provides HoS with crucial instructions for managing the teaching and learning process, which can increase instructors' dedication to their jobs. It shows every method a HoS might use to improve the results of the teaching and learning process. For instance, according to theory, the school's vision and aim should be clearly articulated and conveyed in order to effectively supervise the teaching and learning process. Each teacher should be held to high expectations and performance criteria set by the HoS.

The theory focuses more on classroom teaching and learning processes (the teacher's life inside the classroom). It focused only on the teacher as a professional and ignored personal needs by giving less consideration to factors like social factors. Before beginning the teaching process in the classroom, these elements may, in one way or another, have an impact on teachers' performance. From the focus of this study, an effective HoS leadership strategy should be one that enhances teachers' lives in and outside the classroom (curricular and extracurricular) for quality teaching and learning outcomes.

Instructional leadership theory can be applied in education settings to improve teachers' commitment to work. It addressed different strategies to be used by HoS as instructional leaders to improve the teaching and learning process (Sarkaya & Erdoan, 2016). As a consequence of strong assistance from their dedicated teachers, it is anticipated that the teaching and learning process will boost students' learning and academic accomplishment in their final exams. This can be done by a HoS who focuses on instruction, has a hands-on approach, is goal-oriented, and sets high expectations.

V. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The reviewed related literature was organized according to the research question based on the SSMT HoS Recognition Leadership Strategy on enhancing teachers' commitment. Researchers' contributions to this research mostly concentrated on the elements that affect teachers' commitment and the link between principal leadership style and teachers' commitment. Furthermore, HoS was required to identify who performed their duties as well as praise their

good behavior; by doing so, it increased their level of commitment to work.

Wenno (2016), in Canada, investigated the effect of principal managerial leadership and compensation on physics teacher performance in a senior high school in Baguala District, Ambon. The study was designed under a quantitative paradigm by using a questionnaire for data collection. The findings reported a high correlation existed between principal managerial leadership and teacher performance; compensation and performance; and the combination of principal managerial leadership and compensation with performance.

In contrast to the prior study, the current study covered all subject teachers in CBSS and used the Chi Square Test to assess the association between the HoS Leadership Strategy and teachers' commitment in CBSS in Kilimanjaro. The results of the reviewed study were similar to those from Tanzania, where scientific subjects perform badly in comparison to other subject combinations in six national tests due to a number of reasons, including teachers' recognition and reward (Lyanga & Chen, 2020). What was not clearly addressed in the reviewed study was how recognition was used by HoS to enhance teachers' commitment to their work. Therefore, the current study examined how this strategy is supposed to be applied, whether orally, in writing, or sometimes by giving tangible rewards, for the purpose of appreciating the good job performed by teachers in assisting students' learning and increasing their academic performance in their final examinations.

The study by Thompson (2017) examined teachers' expectations of the leadership of educational leaders and also looked into ways for rewarding and recognizing achievement. The study recommended that principals be encouraged to be more careful and focused in paying attention to the dedication of employees and applauding them, as well as being attentive in keeping all staff members to the highest levels of performance. This was done taking into account the value of acknowledgment. This explains the significance of HoS recognition and, occasionally, rewarding teachers who exhibit a high level of interest in students' learning. In the reviewed study, issues like teachers setting their personal timetable for assisting students with learning difficulties were discussed. The current study considered this one of the indicators of a high level of teachers' commitment, and findings and recommendations were made on how to practice CBSS in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania.

From the perspective of teachers working in high schools, Ucar (2021) in Turkey investigated the impact of distributed leadership behaviors on teachers' organizational commitment. 275 teachers were chosen for the study using a straightforward random sample procedure. The dispersed leadership behaviors of the school principals were used to predict the participant teachers' organizational commitment using regression analysis. The study revealed that the distributed leadership behaviors of school principals were high in the areas of open leadership, school culture, employee involvement, and dynamics, while the organizational commitment levels of teachers were found to be low in the

compliance area but high in the identification and internalization areas.

Despite the positive results of the previous study, it had a different research environment than the current study, which required to determine how useful CBSS is in Kilimanjaro, Tanzania. The student-teacher ratio in these two contexts differs, which can affect teachers' levels of commitment. When considering CBSS, the student-teacher ratio is more than 45:1 (URT, 2015). For this ratio, teachers have a lot to do with students in classroom sessions, extra-curricular activities, and remedial classes. How this teacher is recognized in these schools might differ from high schools.

Additionally, Ucar, (2021) identified a link between teachers' organizational commitment levels and the strategic leadership traits of school principals. The 3648 teachers employed by the secondary educational institutions in Van Province during the 2017–2018 academic year comprised the research universe for the relational screening model. The stratified sampling technique was used to select 558 teachers as the sample for the study. Findings from the study show that teachers believed school leaders exhibited strategic leadership qualities consistently in the areas of transformational applications, managerial applications, and political applications, as well as in the area of ethical applications. The level of teachers' organizational commitment was found to be moderate, with low levels in the internalization and compliance sub-dimensions.

Based on the reviewed study, it suggested that school principals might have an impact on teachers' commitment in various ways, which may also be relevant in CBSS settings. According to its objective, the study did not explore how recognition and leadership dimensions influence teachers' levels of commitment. Due to this, the current study aimed to examine how this leadership dimension, as in the previous study, improves teachers' commitment. Hence, in order to fill this gap, the current study in Tanzania's secondary school settings examines how HoS recognition leadership strategy is employed and improves teachers' level of commitment in CBSS in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania.

In Malaysian secondary schools, Kasa et al. (2020) investigated the impact of a principal's internalized moral perspective on teacher commitment. By upholding subordinates' trust, fulfilling job requirements, and being able to accomplish change despite obstacles, authentic leadership principles served as an alternative to traditional leadership approaches in organizations. A quantitative survey using a standardized questionnaire served as the research methodology. 254 instructors who were randomly chosen from 10 national secondary schools and were supervised by principals made up the study's sample. The level of teachers' organizational commitment was assessed using a questionnaire on organizational commitment. The internalized moral perspective factor of authentic leadership was found to have a substantial impact on teacher commitment.

In trying to determine what organizational leaders should do to affect teachers' commitment, the reviewed study agreed with the findings of the current study. According to what was believed in Tanzania (URT, 2015), if instructors were dedicated to their jobs, it would also boost the academic performance of the school. The reviewed study was limited to principals' internalized moral perspective, while the current study was limited to HoS recognition leadership strategies for teachers' externally recognizable teaching and learning activities. Hence, the current study organized and examined the effective implementation of the HoS recognition leadership strategy on improving teachers' level of commitment in CBSS in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania.

In the same way, Samancioglu et al. (2020) looked into how distributed leadership affected the commitment, organizational citizenship, and job satisfaction of teachers in Gaziantep, Turkey. As a result of the study's findings, teachers' work happiness, organizational citizenship behavior, and organizational commitment all demonstrated a statistically significant relationship with distributed leadership. When it comes to dispersed leadership subdimensions, the cohesive leadership team subdimension only had a statistically significant impact on work satisfaction, however the leadership functions dimension had an impact on organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior as well. Likewise, the current study observed to what extent teachers were committed to their work, as did the reviewed study. In the current study, the researcher reduced the number of aspects under observation in order to deal with them in depth and, from its findings, make critical recommendations that will help to improve teachers' level of commitment in CBSS in Kilimanjaro, Tanzania. The concentration was on aspects of HoS recognition and leadership strategy. The study explored different alternatives that, when applied by HoS, would improve teachers' commitment in CBSS in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania. These include how extracurricular learning activities can be observed by HoS by visiting the classes, laboratories, and organized discussion groups, finding teachers' presence, and appreciating the sport orally or through writing.

Additionally, Cilek (2019) looked into how teachers' organizational commitment in Turkey was affected by the leadership style of school principals. To determine the impact of leadership size on teachers' organizational commitment, meta-analysis was employed as the calculation method. The study of the random effect model's findings revealed that leadership had an extremely powerful and favorable impact on teachers' organizational commitment. Teachers' organizational commitment is more influenced by supporting, democratic, and transformational leadership styles than by other leadership philosophies. The other moderators selected for the research, with the exception of leadership styles, are not significant predictors of the association between school leadership and organizational commitment.

The current study explored more of what was happening in the field as it involved teachers and students, who were the study respondents. The data collected from the field compared to what was found in the documents provided a lot of room for the respondents to explore the real situation in the field. In academic settings, the outcomes take a long time to become vivid. Therefore, it calls on education supervisors to invest in enhancing teachers' commitment so that they devote more of all they have to assist students as the key performance indicators of their commitment. Hence, the current study conducted in CBSS in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania, where the information obtained helped the study report and recommend how teachers' commitment challenges were handled by HoS by applying recognition leadership strategy.

Similar to this, White (2021) investigated how to practice good instructional leadership while serving as a school administrator in order to increase their leadership effectiveness. Relationship building, encouraging growth and performance, and making the most of one's specific circumstances were all part of instructional leadership. Because it still has a significant impact on a school's success, the principal's function as an instructional leader should not be undervalued. The reviewed study concurred with the current study in that it focused on finding a better way of recognizing teachers based on what they were doing at school. The current study's findings aided in understanding the effectiveness of the HoS recognition leadership method and its effects on the levels of commitment among teachers at CBSS in Tanzania's Kilimanjaro Region. Teachers, as the great assertors in education settings, need HoS attention, listening, and being appreciated. By doing so, it enhances their ability to work beyond the set limits, which in turn benefits their learning and academic achievements in their final examination. Hence, a good leader will always focus on encouraging teachers in different ways to work hard for the betterment of the school's goals.

In addition, Setyaningsih & Sunaryo (2021) investigated strategies to enhance self-efficacy, job satisfaction, and transformational leadership strengthening to boost teacher commitment. 1307 non-civil servant middle school teachers in Indonesia's Cirebon District made up the study population, while 136 teachers made up the research sample. The findings indicated that improving transformational leadership, self-efficacy, and job satisfaction could boost teachers' dedication to their profession. On the basis of Sitorem's analysis, the weak indicators were strengthened by being corrected, resulting in the following priority order for addressing the improvement of indicators: For self-efficacy variables, 1. self-confidence strength and 2. self-confidence announcement; 3. salary received; 4. promotions; and 5. supervision of supervisors; for the job satisfaction variable; 6. the job itself; and 7. the self-efficacy variables.

The reviewed study used transformational leadership strategies to improve teachers' levels of commitment, while the current study employed recognition leadership strategies. This shows that leadership strategy is very important in

enhancing teachers' levels of commitment. To increase teachers' level of commitment, it is crucial for a HoS to have a variety of tactics that allow them to be adaptable from one circumstance or context to another. The purpose of the current study was to investigate how teachers are routinely observed by HoS and motivated to work harder when discovered supervising extracurricular activities in their spare time. When they devote their free time to helping slow learners in their remedial programs, how are they recognized? All of these factors prompted the researcher to undertake this study, which compared the Cirebon District in Indonesia to the Kilimanjaro region of Tanzania to see how well the HoS recognition leadership method worked to increase teachers' engagement in CBSS.

In the southern zone of the Sungai Petani District in Kedah, Malaysia, Raman et al. (2015) investigated the connection between principals' leadership style and secondary school teachers' commitment. Teachers' surveys, which were chosen at random from 10 schools, were used to gather the data. The results showed a substantial correlation between teachers' commitment and the leadership styles of principals. The current study, which looked at how leadership style affects teachers' commitment, agreed with the reviewed study in terms of its character. The reviewed study commented generally that school leadership influences teachers' commitment. It was now the role of the current study to examine specifically how recognition leadership strategies enhance teachers' levels of commitment. The study had the role of finding out under what circumstances it is recommended to recognize and appreciate teachers' performance for the purpose of increasing teachers' levels of commitment in CBSS in Kilimanjaro, Tanzania, as proposed by SSMT in URT (2015).

Kean, Kannan, and Piaw (2017) did another study in Malaysia that observed at the connection between teacher dedication and principal leadership strategies. In particular for teaching work, the study indicated that instructor commitment was strong. A greater emphasis should be placed in those programs on activities that have been identified by the study as having an impact on teacher commitment, such as ongoing teaching improvement, teamwork, and school climate.

This study concurred with the reviewed one on the aspects considered in measuring teachers' commitment as well as the aspects under the recognition leadership strategy. Therefore, the current study recommends to all HoS to build up the teachers' recognition and rewarding system, which will enforce teachers' greater commitment to their daily teaching roles and build teamwork and competition among them for better academic outcomes in all CBSS in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania.

At the Islamic school in the southern city of Tangerang in Indonesia, Firdaus, Akuba, and Purnamasari (2019) looked into the effects of leadership, motivation, and perceived workload on teacher commitment. The findings demonstrated that leadership affects commitment by influencing perceived

workload. The findings indicated that in order to boost teachers' commitment, it is important to understand the leadership style of the school's administrators (who serve as their direct supervisors). This will help us understand how much work they believe they have to accomplish and prevent them from feeling overburdened. Despite the two research' distinct study environments, both concluded that the effectiveness of school leadership has an impact on the levels of commitment among teachers. The recent survey also found that there are many pupils in the classrooms at CBSS but few teachers. Based on this fact, teaching in CBSS is tiresome, and if there is no HoS recognition and appreciation for these teachers, their commitment level will always be low. Hence, the study recommended what should be done by HoS for the purpose of increasing teachers' commitment in CBSS in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania, compared to what was reported in Indonesia.

Penezai & Shah (2021) also looked into teachers' perceptions of the leadership styles used by their school principals and how such styles related to the teachers' commitment to their profession. A favorable and moderate association between leadership approach and teacher professional dedication was found by the study's findings. The findings showed that most instructors believed their principals used delegation-oriented leadership styles. It was discovered that teachers were dedicated to their careers as educators. Teachers' commitment to their career was found to be significantly impacted by those who facilitate leadership tactics. According to the study, principals' leadership tactics in Ziarat, Balochistan, have a substantial impact on teachers' professional commitment.

This study concurred with the reviewed study that school leadership strategies influence teachers' levels of commitment in their professional work. Due to this, the researcher examined specifically how the recognition strategy as proposed by SSMT used simple aspects of appreciating, acknowledging, and rewarding teachers' good performance. Different areas, such as remedial teaching, supervising extra-curricular activities, and using personal time to assist slow learners to improve their academic excellence, demanded that the researcher conduct a similar study that examined the effectiveness of the HoS recognition leadership strategy in improving teachers' levels of commitment in CBSS in the Kilimanjaro region of Tanzania.

Ziduli, Buka, Molepo, and Jadezweni (2018) explored the best fundamental leadership styles that principals in rural secondary schools in South Africa might employ to increase teachers' commitment. In the Eastern Cape Province's top-performing rural schools, the study was carried out. It was thought that underperforming schools could pick up tips from performing ones. Successful rural secondary school principals employed democratic and autocratic leadership styles, while laissez-faire leadership styles had a negative impact on the culture of teaching and learning, according to a thematic analysis of the data obtained from interviews. The Department of Basic Education should invest more time and resources on principal leadership development.

The current investigation included both the top-performing and bottom-performing CBSS, in contrast to the prior study. According to the study's findings, teachers require HoS attention, recognition, and appreciation of what they are doing in order to enhance their level of work commitment, regardless of whether their schools are performing well or poorly. Depending on how HoS sets up various recognition techniques, from oral to tangible, teachers' best performance may be elevated to a higher level. Therefore, the current study's goal was to determine how well the HoS recognition leadership method was implemented and how much it increased teachers' levels of commitment in CBSS in Tanzania's Kilimanjaro Region.

Similar to this, Githiari (2017) in Kenya examined the methods by which principals in Nairobi County develop the leadership skills necessary for efficient management of secondary schools. The study's conclusions showed that pre-service, in-service, and on-the-job training were all necessary to develop leadership skills. The reviewed study reported effective management aspects that, when employed by school leadership, can improve teachers' commitment. In the current study, the HoS strategy under investigation did not ask him or her to undergo a process of training in order to be in a position to apply it because the HoS appointed or in leadership since 2015 had already been given this SSMT Kit as their point of reference. What was required was to know these different strategies and the techniques they employed. These aspects were like how HoS uses oral appreciation, incentives, and other psychological recognition to inspire a teacher to do much more in the roles assigned to him or her. That is why the current study specifically places its emphasis on examining how effective the HoS recognition leadership strategy employed to enhance teachers' commitment in CBSS in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania, is.

Ngusa (2018) attempted to identify variables related to teacher involvement in research and publishing in the context of Tanzanian universities in Arusha. The survey found that professors participate in and provide papers at conferences, workshops, and research seminars. This was counted as one of the strategies whereby the junior teachers learn from the experienced ones. They get courage and learn how they were supposed to prepare, and finally, little effort is required from their senior leaders as they learn through observation.

The reviewed study helped to establish an understanding of how educational leadership can use different leadership strategies to enhance junior teachers levels of commitment to their professional work. In its investigation, recognition strategy by using psychological encouragement, oral, written, and other tangible incentives was not highly emphasized as among the many techniques under recognition strategy that can be used to improve teachers' level of commitment. Therefore, the current study investigated and finally recommended different techniques that can be used by HoS to appreciate teachers' performance in all professional dimensions, from classroom to extra-curricular supervision and even supervision of remedial classes in CBSS in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania.

Additionally, Mwesiga & Malusu (2020) investigated the effectiveness of teachers' dedication and school leadership in Tanzania's Kagera Region. The results showed that teachers were highly committed to upholding their teaching duties. The commitment to teaching was, however, constrained by a number of issues, including insufficient training and frequent seminars, workshops, and professional development; ineffective participation in school decision-making; ineffective communication; some inept head teachers; a lack of motivation; and an unappealing working environment.

The current study and the one that was previously examined both focused on factors that increase teachers' commitment levels when used by school administration. HoS in the current study engaged in a few aspects of the recognition strategy as proposed by SSMT. Recognition and appreciation were there in the schools, but they were not structured or designed with the purpose of attaining a certain goal. Therefore, this study recommended different techniques with which they are supposed to engage in their daily activities, which will help improve teachers' levels of commitment in CBSS. These aspects ranged from oral appreciation to the reward system in the school, which states the criteria to be observed so that a teacher can be recognized by being awarded a certificate or given a certain incentive.

The role of school leadership in enhancing organizational and teacher commitment in schools has been highlighted in various studies by Wenno (2016), Ziduli, Buka, Molepo & Jadezweni (2018), Githiari (2017), and Mwesiga & Malusu (2020), according to the reviewed empirical studies on the effective implementation of HoS recognition leadership strategy globally, in Africa, East Africa, and Tanzania in particular. These, however, did not investigate the HoS recognition leadership strategy's efficacy in raising teachers' commitment in community-based secondary schools in Tanzania's Kilimanjaro Region. This knowledge gap made it necessary to carry out the present investigation. The goal of the current study was to determine whether the HoS recognition leadership method was successful in raising teachers' commitment in community-based secondary schools in Tanzania's Kilimanjaro Region.

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A correlational cross-sectional survey design was used in the study as part of a qualitative research methodology. The study looked at how the SSMT HoS recognition leadership strategy was put into practice to raise teacher commitment levels in CBSS in Tanzania's Kilimanjaro Region. Because the sample was chosen from several schools at once to provide a wide number of representatives, this design was adopted. Any survey approach is used to describe the characteristics of respondents in order to develop ideas or generalizations about the community they represent, according to Creswell & Creswell (2018). Additionally, it is utilized to learn more about the current conditions, requirements, and effectiveness of particular programs, goods, or organizations.

The respondents were questioned about their attitudes on the HoS recognition leadership method and the degree of commitment of the teachers, as well as their views, habits, and preferences. As a result, a substantial number of responses were contacted quickly. All 225 community-based secondary schools in the Kilimanjaro region, all 8245 teachers, and 104,160 students were included in the target population. Three district councils were chosen by a random sampling technique. Four schools from each DC (district council) were chosen for the study.

To pick 10 teachers from each school for the study, the researcher utilized a straightforward randomization procedure. Through physical sampling and replacement, the hiring process for teachers was carried out. The activity was repeated with the students in each school, and 20 students were chosen at random to participate in the study. Since every component of the research population had an equal probability of being chosen, the simple random procedure was employed (Leavy, 2017). Additionally, survey research designs with about 350 participants are advised by Creswell & Creswell (2018). Therefore, a total of 360 participants (120 teachers and 240 students) were selected to participate in this study.

By examining the content validity, a panel of specialists in the field of study, including three seasoned researchers and experts in postgraduate studies at Mwenye Catholic University, evaluated the validity of the instruments. Before the instruments were used in the field, their suggestions were taken into consideration and improvements were made to create the final version. The language clarity and ambiguities of the tools were also reviewed, and these research professionals critically evaluated the items to see if they communicated the information being measured (Okendo et al., 2020).

The researcher examined the questionnaire's reliability using the Cronbach's alpha coefficient to determine the reliability of the research instruments for items on the Likert scale. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to apply the algorithm to the questionnaire's Likert scale items, and the alpha for each questionnaire was calculated. In social science research, acceptable dependability is defined as a determined coefficient reliability value of 0.7 or higher (Okendo et al., 2020). Section B Question 3 of the Teachers' Questionnaire had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.974, while Section B Question 3 of the Students' Questionnaire had a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.906. Therefore, the tools were prepared to collect data from the intended audience as long as the numbers were greater than 0.700.

For the analysis of quantitative data, descriptive and inferential statistics were used. Data were gathered using surveys with Likert scales for descriptive statistics. Tables were created after the data was processed using frequencies, percentages, and mean scores. The study question was taken into consideration when interpreting the findings. Using the Chi Square Test, inferential statistics were checked against their presumptions at a 95% confidence level and a 5% significance level. Due to the nature of the data that was

gathered, this strategy was chosen based on its assumptions. Its dependent variable employed categorical data to measure four levels of instructors' commitment and was measured on an ordinal scale (i.e., included Likert items, e.g., a 5-point scale from "strongly agree" through "strongly disagree").

VII. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. HoS Recognition Leadership Strategy

The study examined how HoS recognition leadership strategy contributed on improving teachers' level of commitment in CBSS in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania. Data were principally collected from teachers. Table 2 presents specific research information whereby the Likert scale has five points that the respondent could prefer as SA-strong agree, A=agree, U-undecided, D-disagree, SD-strong disagree, and n = 115.

Table 2: HoS Recognition Leadership Strategy

Statement	SA(%)	A(%)	U(%)	D(%)	SD(%)	Mean \bar{X}
1. My school has recognition and reward system which built teachers' performance competition among us.	42(36.5)	45(39.1)	6(5.2)	18(15.7)	4(3.5)	3.9
2. My HoS offer certificates for teachers who has shown high level of commitment in teaching and extra-curricular duties.	19(16.5)	42(36.5)	7(6.1)	38(33.0)	9(7.8)	3.2
3. My HoS words of encouragement to teachers reduced social distance and enhanced me even to share my personal secrete for attainment.	32(27.8)	52(45.2)	6(5.2)	20(17.4)	5(4.3)	3.7
4. As we teachers being sure that any good performance will be appreciated by HoS even orally no one is left behind in devoting our time for teaching.	37(32.2)	53(46.1)	6(5.2)	15(13.0)	4(3.5)	3.9
5. In our school the spirit of recognition is working both to teachers and HoS when each one accomplish his roles.	27(23.5)	65(56.5)	7(6.1)	12(10.4)	4(3.5)	3.9
6. I dare to rank number one this strategy among other HoS strategies with immediate effect in teachers' commitment to work.	35(30.4)	60(52.2)	7(6.1)	11(9.6)	2(1.7)	4.0
7. This strategy enabled us to improve students' performance.	42(36.5)	55(47.8)	6(5.2)	8(7.0)	4(3.5)	4.1
8. No period left untaught as far as teachers knows that whoever accomplish his / her job will be appreciated.	38(33.0)	53(46.1)	4(3.5)	17(14.8)	3(2.6)	3.9
9. My HoS has formal and informal ways of recognizing teachers' accomplishment.	39(33.9)	54(47.0)	7(6.1)	10(8.7)	5(4.3)	4.0
10. I acknowledge my HoS recognition and reward system established in my school.	33(28.7)	62(53.9)	5(4.3)	8(7.0)	7(6.1)	3.9
11. The more HoS use varied recognition techniques the more he / she wins teachers' commitment to work.	34(29.6)	63(54.8)	6(5.2)	10(8.7)	2(1.7)	4.0
12. I feel more valued as my HoS appreciate my performance.	42(36.5)	45(39.1)	7(6.1)	8(7.0)	3(2.6)	3.7
13. When school academic performance seemed to be high, I associated it with my HoS recognition and rewarding the employees.	38(33.0)	54(47.0)	3(2.6)	13(11.3)	7(6.1)	3.9
14. In my school teachers are enthusiastically motivated as HoS pay attention to our human needs.	36(31.3)	63(54.8)	0(0.0)	12(10.4)	4(3.5)	4.0
Average Mean						3.9

Source: Field Data (2020)

Data in Table 2 indicates statements on how the HoS Recognition Leadership Strategy was implemented in CBSS in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania. The findings indicated that at a mean of 4.1(82%), teachers agreed on the aspect that the HoS recognition strategy enabled them to work hard, and as a result, the students' academic performance increased from time to time. This implies that the majority (i.e., 82%) of HoS in CBSS in Kilimanjaro Region know the implications of recognizing teachers in their schools. This method is employed to enhance students' academic performance on final exams, which is the result of teachers' dedication to their jobs. This was backed up by Thompson (2017), who contended that educators' expectations of educational leaders' leadership should consider the value of recognition, encourage them to be more deliberate and focused in recognizing and praising staff members' commitment, and be vigilant in holding all employees to the highest standards of performance.

Furthermore, this can be done in different ways, like with a word of appreciation once a teacher accomplishes a certain assignment. Sometimes by preparing a special card of appreciation for teachers in one of the subject departments after getting a national examination result and being ranked as the first subject with high average performance in the school. This can be done during Form 4 graduation, where school board members and parents attend. The experience shows that teachers feel their efforts are highly valued towards students' academic excellence and trigger a spirit of working very hard so that they can maintain their position. Even other departments will work hard so that next time they get such recognition. Hence, having a well-structured rewarding system will inculcate a good spirit of competition among subject departments, and finally, the students will benefit more as they will get enough teachers' support during their teaching and learning process. Even the HoS, school board, and all other education supervisors will be recognized, though it was started by a single individual teacher's recognition in a school.

Additionally, findings in Table 2 illustrated that at a mean of 4.0 (80%), teachers agreed that they could dare to rank HoS recognition leadership strategy number one among other HoS leadership strategies as it has an immediate effect on their commitment to work. Another aspect agreed upon at this mean was that HoS had formal and informal ways of recognizing teachers' accomplishments; the more HoS use varied recognition techniques, the more they win their commitment to work, and in their schools, they are enthusiastically motivated as HoS pay attention to their human needs. This implies that teachers in the CBSS like much recognition and should be formalized in order to avoid any kind of personal bias.

This finding was in line with those of Ucar (2021), who looked at how high school teachers' organizational commitment was affected by the dispersed leadership behaviors of school principals. Teachers were highly motivated as their school principals appreciated them and demanded it be a continuous culture in their schools as it enhanced good performance. It is also the role of the HoS to

set very formal procedures, especially for those kinds of recognition that require some expenses to be offset from school revenues. Sometimes it can be organized in such a way that parents and the school board can contribute to this through parent contributions or through school income-generating projects. The outcome of all these will benefit the students' learning and academic performance, and the whole school community will be considered the school that cares for teachers' jobs.

On the other hand, the finding in Table 2 indicated that, at a mean of 3.9 (78%), teachers were neutral in different aspects concerning HoS recognition and leadership strategy. These aspects were like how the HoS recognition and reward system in their schools has built teachers' performance competition among them. To what extent teachers' were appreciated by their HoS orally for their good performance; also, was there any period left untaught as far as teachers knew that whoever accomplished his or her job would be appreciated; they acknowledged their HoS recognition and reward system established in their schools; when school academic performance seemed to be high, they associated it with their HoS recognition and rewarding them? All these implies that still there some issues which are not yet understood by HoS about recognition leadership strategy so that it can be practiced smoothly. On the other hand, some HoS are not involving teachers' in planning how recognition and rewarding systems can be implemented in their schools.

This result was in contrast to Kirkiç & Balci's (2021) conclusion that school administrators did not absorb the values of their organizations whereas teachers generally did. The institutional commitment of teachers was also crucial for the growth of students. In order to maintain the high levels of dedication among preschool teachers, administrators need be aware of their own leadership styles. If all these are not taken care of, the effect of all this might be that teachers remain unappreciated as they try at their level best to accomplish the roles entrusted to them, and finally, it might affect students' learning and their academic performance. This is because teachers in this study were considered the key to school academic excellence.

The mean (\bar{X}) of 3.7 (74%) in table 2 indicated teachers were undecided or were neutral about the following aspects of their HoS recognition strategy: their HoS words of encouragement to them reduced social distance and enhanced them even to share their personal secrets for attainment; they felt more valued as their HoS appreciated their performance. This implies that teachers failed to have evidence of whether such aspects were practiced by their HoS. That means they did not have enough evidence from their HoS that they use words that encourage them in their performance in such a way that they can consider them friends or parents.

This was corroborated by Ucar & Dalgic (2021), who found a connection between teachers' organizational commitment levels and the strategic leadership traits of school principals. A low level in the compliance sub-dimension, a low level in the internalization sub-dimension, and a moderate level in the identification sub-dimension were

observed for teachers' organizational commitment. Lacking this kind of relationship in a school creates a very big gap and distance, whereby even a HoS can fail to get teachers' feedback on what is taking place in the school. To correct this, the HoS should be alerted about the importance and effect of lacking these aspects for the better running of the school.

Furthermore, the mean (\bar{X}) of 3.2 (64%) in table 2 indicated teachers were undecided or were neutral that during school events their HoS offer certificates for teachers who had shown a high level of commitment in teaching and extracurricular duties. This implies that in their schools, such a program was not there, which is why teachers were not sure if it was there or not. Moreover, HoS were not aware of how much teachers feel valued when their performance is recognized by their school leader.

This finding was contrary to Setyaningsih & Sunaryo (2021), who suggested that teachers' recognition should be formalized in all educational institutions where all important criteria to be considered should be well known by school

principals and teachers. When a teacher's performance is discovered to be higher in subject performance in the national test solely, HoS may occasionally believe that this is permissible. But even the environment teacher in charge, the discipline teacher, and others can also be recognized in their performance. Therefore, HoS should not limit themselves to academic performance alone; they are supposed to view recognition as a broader aspect of enhancing teachers' commitment.

B. Teachers' Level of Commitment

The study searched for teachers' levels of commitment to their core function as teaching professionals. The responses presented resulted from the question, "What is the evidence of teachers' level of commitment at work in Kilimanjaro Community-Based Secondary Schools?". Responses from students through their questionnaire are presented in Table 3. Teachers' levels of commitment were highly committed (HC), committed (C), low committed (LC), and not committed (NC).

Table 3: Teachers' Level of Commitment

Statement	HC(%)	C(%)	LC(%)	NC(%)	Mean \bar{X}
1. My teachers attend classes according to the set time table.	136(56.7)	88(36.7)	15(6.3)	1(0.4)	3.5
2. My teachers encourage us to work in groups and also assist our groups on how to perform better academically.	134(55.8)	100(41.7)	5(2.1)	1(0.4)	3.5
3. My teachers enabled me to improve my performance this term compared to last term.	139(57.9)	92(38.3)	6(2.5)	3(1.3)	3.5
4. My teachers find private time at school to teach us periods that were absent at school.	71(29.6)	97(40.4)	44(18.3)	28(11.7)	2.9
5. My class teacher used to ask my parent where I am when I was absent to school.	71(29.6)	98(40.8)	45(18.8)	26(10.8)	2.9
6. My teachers before punishing students used to take time to understand our problem first and help us.	51(21.3)	84(35.0)	62(25.8)	43(17.9)	2.6
7. I feel safer and freer to share with my teachers about my internal life challenges.	41(17.1)	101(42.1)	61(25.4)	37(15.4)	2.6
Average Mean (\bar{X})	101(42.1)	100(41.7)	26(10.8)	13(5.4)	3.0

Source: Field Data (2020)

From Table 3, the data reported the overall average mean of (\bar{X}) 3.0 (75.0%) of all students' responses about their teachers' level of commitment. This means that teachers were moderately committed to their professional roles, which helps facilitate quality teaching and learning processes. This also implies that HoS played their role of attending to teachers' professional and social needs, which gives them courage and the desire to work hard on helping students' learning. This finding is supported by instructional theory, which stipulates HoS behaviors that, once practiced, help teachers feel that they are charged with students' learning (Sarkaya & Erdoan, 2016).

Responses in Table 3 revealed how teachers were committed to students' learning. Data reported at average mean (\bar{X}) 3.5 (87.5%): teachers encourage students to work in groups and also assist their groups on how to perform better academically; teachers attend classes according to the set time table; teachers try to come up with different teaching

methods that make me understand more about the subject; teachers enable students to improve their performance from one term to another. These measures of teachers' commitment suggest that if the HoS wants to see truly committed teachers in their schools, they should set standards and create efficient systems that ensure that teachers automatically follow those standards. By carrying out these actions, the school will experience excellence in the teaching and learning process, with good student academic performance on their final exams and positive staff relationships serving as indications. Kean, Kannan, and Piau's (2017) study on teacher commitment indicated that instructors were highly committed, particularly to their teaching jobs, which corroborated these findings.

Furthermore, from Table 3, data revealed an average mean of (\bar{X}) 2.6 (65.2%) to 2.9 (79.0%) as teachers' low level of commitment. Areas that revealed this were: teachers didn't find private time at school to teach students periods that were lost due to their absence at school; class teachers didn't ask

students' parents where they were when they were absent from school; teachers, before punishing students, didn't take time to understand students' problems first and help them; students didn't feel safer and freer to share with their teachers about their internal life challenges. All this implies that teachers were just going to school to fulfil the law requirement of attending school in order to earn a salary at the end of the month. This was contrary to Mgonja (2017), who argued that the HoS was charged with making sure that the teaching and learning process took place smoothly by applying different techniques and strategies when supervising teachers. And for applying the effective HoS leadership strategies in place, it was expected that teachers would be committed to their job by raising their performance standards with minimal supervision.

C. Hypothesis Test

The researcher was interested in testing a hypothesis to check if there is a relationship between HoS recognition leadership strategy and teachers' level of commitment in CBSS in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania. The results are summarized in Table 4.

H_0 : There is no significant relationship between HoS Recognition Leadership Strategy and Teachers' Level of Commitment.

D. Assumptions

- It was assumed that both variables were categorical (i.e., scores were not used). That is, both variables take on values that are names or labels.
- All observations were independent. It was assumed that every observation in the dataset was independent. That is, the value of one observation in the dataset does not affect the value of any other observation.
- Cells in the contingency table were mutually exclusive. It was assumed that individuals could only belong to one cell in the contingency table. That is, cells in the table were mutually exclusive; an individual could not belong to more than one cell.

E. Decision Rules

Decision Rule under a significant level of $\alpha = 0.05$ (two-tailed): -

- If the value of p is $> (0.05)$, the null hypothesis (H_0) will be accepted and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) rejected.
- However, if the value of p will be (0.05) , the Null H_0 will be rejected and the alternative hypothesis H_1 will be accepted.

Before testing the hypothesis, the researcher checked the assumptions and observed and tested the hypothesis.

Table 4: The Chi-Square Test for Null hypothesis H_0 .

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	22.149 ^a	9	.019
Likelihood Ratio	24.132	9	.013
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.727	1	.911
N of Valid Cases	240		
Source: Field Data (2020)			
Note: 6 cells (7.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .08.			

The results of the analysis in Table 2 showed that the value of $p(0.019)$ was less than $\alpha(0.05)$. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected and an alternative hypothesis (H_1) was accepted.

Hence, there was a significant relationship between HoS recognition leadership strategy and teachers' levels of commitment, as supported by Mahzan & Nordin (2021), who argued that for effective HoS leadership strategies to be in place, it is expected that teachers are committed to their job. This implies that in order for the HoS to win teachers' commitment to their profession and extracurricular activities at school, he or she should apply this leadership strategy. It demands that the head of school use a formal and informal recognition leadership strategy that acknowledges teachers' performance, ranging from oral appreciation to reward certificates or the use of incentives from the school budget. This makes a teacher feel more valued and cared for, which in turn helps them give maximum value during the teaching and learning process and enhance students' academic achievement.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The study concluded that every teacher is professionally accountable for students' learning, observing professional rules and regulations in order to increase their level of commitment. Therefore, when teaching, they must display their personal competence, knowledge, abilities, beliefs, and determinations as one of the variables that could impact their teaching commitment. Apart from that, heads of schools are charged with supervising teachers in their daily professional performance, assisting them to solve their professional challenges, and applying appropriate leadership strategies to improve commitment to work. There was a significant relationship between HoS recognition leadership strategy and teachers' level of commitment in community-based secondary schools in the Kilimanjaro region of Tanzania.

IX. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher would like to bring forward the following recommendations:

The Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology should insist on the application of the HoS Recognition Leadership Strategy as outlined in the Secondary School

Management Toolkit (SSMT), Practical Guide for Heads of Schools. Regional and District Education Authorities should do regular visits to assess how HoS use recognition strategies to improve teachers' commitment in community-based secondary schools in Kilimanjaro Region, Tanzania.

The HoS should acknowledge teachers' performance in the classroom teaching and learning process, environment cleaning, guidance, and counselling departments in order for every teacher to realize that what he or she is doing is valued by his or her HoS. Teachers should keep improving students' academic performance in their national examination results as a result of their commitment. They should engage in students' learning by effectively supervising extra-curricular activities, ensuring punctuality to school and to class, reducing students' indiscipline cases, and encouraging unity, cooperation, and teamwork. Doing all these will position you in higher-ranking community-based secondary schools in Kilimanjaro in the form four national examination results.

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